

CURING AND DEFORMATION ANALYSIS IN SMC COMPRESSION MOLDING

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SUMMARY: Cure and flow behavior of SMC during compression molding are rather complicated due to heat generation, heterogeneous material and so on. This paper describes numerical analysis method for both cure and flow behavior of SMC in order to establish total CAE system for SMC compression molding. Analytical method of cure behavior was combined between numerical and experimental method. The heat generation was determined by both data and defined as function of temperature inside of SMC. This heat generation function was used in the unsteady heat conduction analysis. The most important flow behavior which was clarified by experiment was slippage flow. The slippage flow occurs in both interlamina and intralamina, and this flow behavior influence on distribution of fiber content fraction in products, that leads to scattering for the mechanical properties of products. In order to understand slippage flow behavior three-dimensional large deformation elastic-plastic analysis was used. The calculated results were in good agreement with the experimental results. These analyses proposed were included into total CAE system for SMC compression molding.

KEY WORDS: SMC compression molding, curing, heat generation, initial deformation, slippage flow, hybrid experimental-numerical approach, elastic-plastic analysis, CAE system

INTRODUCTION

SMC (Sheet Molding Compound) is typical fiber reinforced plastics for high volume processing and has been used in structural parts of transportation vehicles, water tank, bathtub and so on. They have high surface appearance, so that exterior applications are also attractive. In order to obtain high strength of molded products long fiber and/or high volume fraction SMC has been developed. Although recycle problems for protecting the earth environment are appeared, SMC will be still major fiber reinforced plastics in terms of volume of productions. Accordingly, there have been many research works related to SMC product from both academia and industry. The publish works were roughly divided into three categories; one is the material aspects such as resin, low profile additives, and the effects material system on properties of molded products [1-5]. The second one is the fabrication system including CAE system [6-14]. The third one is some defects appeared in the products [15-17].

However for designing of SMC products and compression mold, there is no unified approach. The reasons are concentrated to two points; one is material flow and the other is curing

behavior. SMC flow pattern during compression molding is very complicated because reinforcing fibers move together with matrix. As mentioned in the former paragraph Tucker made very practical work for flow pattern of SMC and developed software [18], however essential or characteristics flow behavior can not be solved because it did not consider the effects of reinforcing fibers and also laminated materials. The second point is curing behavior that affects post-deformation state of products after the products removed from the mold. The analysis of curing process is difficult due to heterogeneous materials containing many different components. Fiber orientation state of SMC moldings also greatly affects on post-deformation. Another difficulty of curing analysis is that final curing state is determined through temperature distribution from the beginning of compression process and material thermal properties. Basically SMC material changes their state from liquid to solid because of curing phenomenon, so that the thermal properties such as heat conductivity, thermal expansion and so on are changed abruptly. The material data base for these properties is not establishes and these are changed easily by changing their contents. On the other hand a set of mold would be expensive, so that changing mold design according to try and error method is inconvenient. In order to overcome these problems, CAE system is required for a mold design.

In this paper we propose total CAE system shown in Fig.1. The CAE system was constructed by several parts. In each part numerical analysis methods were developed by using commercial numerical software and/or original program that were mainly finite element method. The establishment of the CAE system is based on following process. First, once material is set into the cavity, and later temperature inside the material increases because of heat transfer from hot mold to material. Next, the upper mold moves downward and material is deformed with slippage flow at interlamina and intralamina of SMC. After initial deformation of material, resin with fibers flows and the mold cavity is filled with them. At then, it is necessary to consider anisotropy of viscosity that affects on the flow pattern. At the curing process, we need to understand distribution of degree of cure and temperature that affect on occurrence of thermal stress and post-deformation. Especially we have to consider thermal history during process. Finally, above analysis results apply to design of stiffness and strength of products.

This paper describes usefulness of the total CAE system. Particularly, a new original method was introduced to analysis of curing process, which enable to understand curing profile during flow stage and curing stage.

HEAT GENERATION AND CURING ANALYSIS

Analysis

Three dimensional heat conduction analysis was performed, in which heat generation due to chemical reaction was included. The curing phenomenon was considered through the heat generation term in the equation of three dimensional heat conduction and the construction method for this term was the most important in this analysis. The basic equation was:

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_x \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + k_y \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + k_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + Q \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density, c is the specific heat, k_x , k_y and k_z are thermal conductivity for x-, y- and z-direction respectively. In order to create the heat generation term the difference of increase of temperature between system with and without heat generation was paid attention. The first system was performed by actual materials and the numerical analysis was used for latter system. We assume that material is set in a heated mold and then heat is conducted from the mold into the material. Temperature inside material increases and reaches to the temperature of heated mold eventually in the case of system without heat generation, whereas the temperature increases rapidly and exceeds the heated mold temperature in the case of system with heat generation. Typical examples are shown in Fig.2 for both cases.

Fig.3 shows finite element division for three dimensional heat conduction analysis in which solid elements were used. Boundary conditions are follows; temperature is fixed on planes-ABCD and -KLM because of mold surface, and planes-ABK and -ADM are symmetrical plane, so that adiabatic boundary conditions are applied. The increase of temperature for system without heat generation as shown in Fig.2 was obtained from the center point by using this analysis. The differences between the analysis and the experiment were caused by the heat generation, so that calorific value was obtained as following equation.

$$\rho c \frac{\Delta T_2 - \Delta T_1}{\Delta t} - Q = 0 \quad (2)$$

where ΔT_1 and ΔT_2 are temperature increment in time variation Δt of the experiment and analysis respectively, and the derivation of the above equation was mentioned in Appendix part briefly.

First calorific value was calculated as function of time corresponding to temperature-time curve and also cumulative calorific value was defined through time as well. The relation between calorific value and time was rewritten to that between calorific value and temperature at the center. Accordingly, heat generation term was defined by the temperature inside material. When temperature reaches a specific value, material emits heat stepwise. The degree of cure was defined as the ratio of sum of heat generation, ΣQ , to total heat generation, $[\Sigma Q]_{Total}$, as follows.

$$\alpha = \frac{\Sigma Q}{[\Sigma Q]_{Total}} \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, curing was completed when α was 0.8 in the analytical region[19]. The curing profile could be practical by using this assumption.

This analytical method was combination between numerical and experimental method, and recently this method was called Hybrid Experimental-Numerical approach for a determination problem.

Results

Fig.2 shows temperature-time curves obtained by experiment and numerical analysis without heat generation. The heat generation occurred from about 130. Using these results, calorific value calculated as function of time and also cumulative calorific value defined through time

as well are shown in Figs.4 and 5 respectively. Total calorific value could be calculated and was estimated about 7.010^{-5} kcal/mm³ as shown in Fig.5. The relation between calorific value and time was rewritten to that between heat generation and temperature at the center. Fig.6 shows this relation. Consequently, heat generation term could be defined by the temperature inside of material. In order to confirm the validity of this method the heat generation function obtained was introduced into heat conduction analysis. Fig.2 also shows result of this analysis. Temperature-time curve obtained by numerical analysis was good agreement with the experimental result.

Curing profile of cross section through thickness direction obtained by numerical analysis is shown in Fig.7. At holding time 210 sec, curing of the bottom layer was completed firstly. At holding time 250 sec, curing of the top layer was also done. Then, curing have progressed toward the center at holding time 315 sec, curing of all region was completed finally. Where 'holding time' was defined as time kept material surface in contact with closing upper mold until start of compression.

In this way, cure behavior in the initial process stage was asymmetry through thickness direction due to considering with the upper mold closing time. Consequently, it seemed that practical curing profile could be obtained by this numerical analysis method.

DEFORMATION ANALYSIS

Analysis

As mentioned in Introduction part the flow pattern is very complicated aspects in SMC compression molding due to effects of fiber and cure state. Particularly, at the initial stage a characteristic flow/deformation states appears as shown in Fig.8. Fig.8 shows side view of the initial stage in the case of three layered SMC. (a) shows that upper and lower layers deforms precedent to the middle layer, on the other hand (b) shows the preceding middle layer. The slippage flow was common phenomena that occur at the inter- and intra-lamina. Normally, decrease of viscosity or elastic modulus of materials due to heat conduction creates the case of (a), and cured upper/lower layers tend to make the cases of (b).

Basically viscosity or elastic modulus of materials decreases with increase of temperature due to thermal diffusion. This situation does not consider the chemical reaction and chemical diffusion; that is $\dot{\epsilon} = 0$. Once chemical reaction occurs these material constants would depend on the degree of cure and increase dramatically as shown in Fig.9. The dependence of material constants on temperature could be easily measured, however the dependence on degree of cure hardly be measured. In this paper an appropriate assumption was made for analyzing deformation state that was affected by both thermal and chemical diffusion.

Fig.3 shows finite element division for the initial deformation analysis of three layers. Boundary conditions are follows; nodes on the plane-KLM were fixed for x-, y- and z-direction, nodes on the plane-ADM and the plane-ABK of neutral planes were fixed for x- and y-direction respectively. Nodes on the plane-ABCD were fixed for x- and y-direction and were given prescribed displacement -0.1 mm every one step for z-direction.

After heat conduction analysis with heat generation term described in the previous section was performed, material constants were determined according to the former discussion. In order to

express slippage flow double nodes were set between not only interlamina layers but also intralamina layers. When the difference of shearing strain adjacent elements exceeds a critical value, it was assumed that separation of the double nodes was initiated. The material model used in this analysis was elastic-plastic relations.

Results

Fig.10 shows deformation state in the case of uniform material constants. The material constants are same in all the elements, so that frictional effects were appeared at the top and bottom surface. The separation occurred at the interlamina. Fig.11(a) shows the actual cases in which heat conduction analysis was performed and also dependence of material constants on temperature was considered. The lower layer was heated by the mold until upper mold touched the upper layer and the period of this time was 30 seconds. The slippage flow was initiated between lower layer and middle layer and therefore lower layer deformed precedent to the middle layer. Fig.11(b) shows another example in which more 6 seconds have passed since deformation state was above state. It was easy to imagine that both upper and lower layers were heated up and material constants were decreased due to thermal diffusion in both layers. The deformation state was very similar to the case as shown in Fig.8(a).

Fig.12 shows the case of extreme long keeping time in which the change of material constants due to curing was considered. After upper mold touched the materials 100 seconds were kept at the same condition. At both upper and lower layers cure occurred and therefore material constants were dramatically increased. The slippage flow initiated both sides of middle layer and finally middle layer was squeezed out. This result was similar to the case as shown in Fig.8(b).

The initial deformation state including slippage flow would affect greatly flow behavior of materials and also fiber orientation of reinforcing fibers, and further post deformation behavior would be caused. According to cure state the initial deformation was changed drastically and this phenomenon indicates an importance of analysis for cure state, so that analytical method proposed in this paper were very useful technique and enable determine molding condition such as mold temperature, closing speed of press machine that related to time to touch the materials and so on. Practically these molding conditions could be determined considering into material characteristics, because different composition of materials made different thermal properties. As shown in previous section the analytical method was suitable for actual material system, therefore proposed method could select molding conditions corresponding to each material.

CONCLUSION

This paper described analytical method for cure state and initial deformation state of SMC during compression molding. The most important result was that database for heat generation due to chemical reaction could be established by Hybrid Experimental-Numerical approach and further the degree of cure was calculated. The initial deformation state was calculated by three dimensional finite element analysis and particularly slippage flow between inter- and intra-lamina was considered. The cure state was very delicate because keeping time of mold affected dramatically and accordingly the initial state was also changed.

REFERENCES

1. Atkins, K.E., "Advances in Pigmentation of Low Profile Composites", *Proceedings the 51st Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 5-7, 1996, Session 13-D.
2. Kan, W.-M.J., Lee, L.J., "LPA Performance in Low Temperature BMC/SMC", *Proceedings the 51st Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 5-7, 1996, Session 2-A.
3. Kinkelaar, M., Muzumdar, S., Lee, L.J., "Analysis of LPA Mechanism by Dilatometry Study", *Proceedings the 49th Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 7-9, 1994, Session 5-C.
4. Young, J.J., Lucas, R.L., Wade, C.B., "A New Versatile Class A SMC Resin", *Proceedings the 51st Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 5-7, 1996, Session 22-D.
5. Kia, H.G., Viscomi, P.V., "High-Pressure/High-Temperature Dilatometry", *Proceedings the 49th Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 7-9, 1994, Session 5-F.
6. Barone, M.R., Caulk, D.A., "A Model for the Flow of a Chopped Fiber Reinforced Polymer Compound in Compression Molding", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol.53, 1986, pp361-371.
7. Sun, E.M., Davis, B.A., Osswald, T.A., "Modeling and Simulation of Thick Compression Molded Parts", *Proceedings the 50th Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., January 30-February 1, 1995, Session 15-B.
8. Twu, J.-T., Hill, R.R., Wang, T.J., Lee, L.J., "Numerical Simulation of Non-Isothermal SMC (Sheet Molding Compound) Molding", *Polymer Composites*, Vol.14, No.6, 1993, pp.503-514.
9. Chang, S.-H., Osswald, T.A., "Predicting Shrinkage and Warpage of Fiber-Reinforced Composite Parts", *Polymer Composites*, Vol.15, No.4, 1994, pp.270-277.
10. Fan, J.D., Lee, L.J., "Optimization of Polyester Sheet Molding Compound. Part II: Theoretical Modeling", *Polymer Composites*, Vol.7, No.4, 1993, pp.250-260.
11. Xu, J., Kim, J., Ho, T., Lee, L.J., "Compression Molding of Sheet Molding Compounds in Plate-Rib Type Geometry", *Polymer Composites*, Vol.14, No.14, 1993, pp.51-52.
12. Hirai, T., "A New Continuous Fabrication System for SMC-Roll Forming", *Proceedings the 51st Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 5-7, 1996, Session 2-C.
13. Collister, J.E., Butler, K.I., Rinz, J.E., "Hydraulically-Assisted Compression Molding Material and Process Development", *Proceedings the 51st Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 5-7, 1996, Session 2-B.
14. Richey, T.A., "Development of a Modular, Automatic SMC Charge Pattern Cutter", *Proceedings the 49th Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 7-9, 1994, Session 18-A.

15. Atkins, K.E., Seats, R.L., Montagne, M.H.P., Behar, G., “Advances in Thermoset Injection Molding Part IV: Knitline and Elevated Temperature Properties in Thermoset Composites”, *Proceedings the 48th Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 8-11, 1993, Session 12-D.
16. Yamada, H., Mihata, I., Tomiyama, T., Walsh, S.P., “Investigation of the Fundamental Causes of Pinholes in SMC Moldings”, *Proceedings the 47h Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 3-6, 1992, Session 1-B.
17. Halvarsson, S., Petterson, J., Nilson, P., “Critical Molding Conditions for Blistering During Compression Molding of Sheet Molding Compound (SMC)”, *Proceedings the 48th Annual Conference on The Society of the Plastic Industry*, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S., February 8-11, 1993, Session 17-C.
18. Tucker, C.L., “Compression Molding of Polymer and Composites”, *Injection and Compression Molding Fundamentals*, Isayev, A. I., ed., Marcel Dekker Inc., New York and Basel, 1987, pp481-565.
19. Barone, M.R., Caulk, C.A., “Effect of Deformation and Thermoset Cure on Heat Conduction in a Chopped Fiber Reinforced Polyester During Compression Molding”, *Int. J. Heat and mass Transfer*, Vol.22, 1979, pp1021-1032.

APPENDIX

The heat conduction equation without the heat generation was shown by equation (a-1).

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_x \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + k_y \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + k_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \quad (\text{a-1})$$

where ρ is the density, c is the specific heat, k_x , k_y and k_z are thermal conductivity for x-, y- and z-direction respectively.

Boundary conditions were shown by following equation.

$$\begin{cases} T = T_0 & (\text{the boundary } S_1) \\ q = q_0 & (\text{the boundary } S_2) \end{cases} \quad (\text{a-2})$$

Equations (a-1) and (a-2) were applied to the principle of virtual work, then following equation could be obtained.

$$\int_v \left\{ \delta T \rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - k_x \frac{\partial \delta T}{\partial x} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - k_y \frac{\partial \delta T}{\partial y} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} - k_z \frac{\partial \delta T}{\partial z} \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right\} dv = 0 \quad (\text{a-3})$$

It was considered that the internal energy, Q , was caused by a chemical diffusion and depended on material temperature, moreover, this was given every step of each temperature. Then following equation could be obtained.

$$\int_v \left\{ \delta T \rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - k_x \frac{\partial \delta T}{\partial x} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - k_y \frac{\partial \delta T}{\partial y} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} - k_z \frac{\partial \delta T}{\partial z} \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right\} dv + \sum_i Q_w \Delta_i \delta T = 0 \quad (\text{a-4})$$

where Q_w and Δ_i represent the energy at the point x_i and the delta function (1 : at the coordinate of the point x_i , 0 : at the coordinates except the point x_i) respectively. System 1 and system 2 were named by systems for equation (a-3) and (a-4) respectively. Here some assumptions were written as follows.

1. Some property values were constant independent of both systems and material temperature.
2. The heat generation at minute region without temperature distribution occur uniformly.
3. The heat conduction terms of temperature gradient for both systems were equal in minute time.

The internal energy $Q (=Q_w\Delta_i)$ which was given by the differences between systems 1 and 2 could be shown by the equation (a-5).

$$\rho c \left(\left[\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \right]_2 - \left[\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \right]_1 \right) - Q = 0 \tag{a-5}$$

It could be considered that the internal energy represents heat generation due to the chemical diffusion. Equation (a-5) could modify following equation for finite time Δt .

$$\rho c \frac{\Delta T_2 - \Delta T_1}{\Delta t} - Q = 0 \tag{a-6}$$

ΔT_1 is temperature increment for system 1 without heat generation

ΔT_2 is temperature increment for system 2 with heat generation

The heat generation per unit time and volume could be obtained by equation (a-6).

Figure 1: Total CAE system for SMC compression molding.

Figure 2: Temperature-time curve.

Figure 3: Finite element division.

Fig.4 Relation between heat generation during cure and time.

Figure 5: Cumulative heat generation versus time.

Figure 6: Relation between heat generation during cure and temperature.

Figure 7: Curing profiles obtained by numerical analysis.

Figure 8: Schematic drawing of a characteristic flow/deformation states at the initial stage.

Figure 9: Typical viscosity variation during SMC compression molding.

Figure 10: Deformed mesh in the case of uniform material constants.

Figure 11a: Deformed mesh in the case of holding time 0 sec (10th step).

Figure 11 b: Deformed mesh in the case of holding time 0 sec (20th step).

Figure 12: Deformed mesh in the case of holding time 100 sec (20th step).